

OGC Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot: Typhoons and Atmospheric Report Section (D130)

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Abstract

The D130 Typhoons and Atmospheric Engineering Report (ER) Section provides a detailed analysis focused on the tracking, forecasting, and impact-based modeling of tropical cyclones (TCs) utilizing both machine learning (ML) and physics-based models. This study leverages various datasets and workflows to enhance the prediction of TC paths, intensity, and induced rainfall, aligning with the broader objectives of the Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot 2024 (CDRP 2024). A total of 13 models, including digital datasets, Python toolboxes, and advanced statistical and physics-based ML models, were explored to evaluate their performance in TC tracking and forecasting. Key components include the evaluation of cloud-based processing capabilities, the integration of Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards to ensure interoperability and reproducibility, and the analysis of meteorological models to interpret data patterns indicative of extreme weather events. The report presents the review methodology, key findings, and recommendations for future research and standardization efforts. Emphasis is placed on the need for robust ML-based algorithms and integrative approaches to achieve accurate path predictions, wind and rainfall forecasts, and storm surge forecasts. The integration of early warning flood impact analysis with TC impact prediction models demonstrates significant potential for improving disaster mitigation and anticipatory action. The findings underscore the critical importance of multi-source data integration, real-time data from in-situ observations and satellites, and the application of advanced statistical processing techniques. This comprehensive approach aims to enhance predictive accuracy and efficiency, contributing to improved disaster preparedness and response.

Keywords: Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot (CDRP), Engineering Report (ER), Tropical Cyclone (TC), Machine Learning (ML)

1. Introduction

Tropical Cyclones (TCs) are among the most devastating natural phenomena, characterized by intense winds, heavy rainfall, and storm surges that can lead to significant loss of life and property. Historically, the tracking and forecasting of TCs have posed

considerable challenges due to their complex and dynamic nature. Over the decades, advancements in meteorological science, satellite technology, and computational models have greatly improved our ability to monitor and predict TC behavior. Analyzing historical patterns of TCs has provided valuable insights into their formation, intensity, and trajectory, enabling better preparedness and response strategies. By examining long-term data and leveraging modern machine learning (ML) and physics-based models, we aim to enhance the accuracy of TC predictions and mitigate their impacts on vulnerable communities.

The Typhoons and Atmospherics ER Section records key components and ML-based workflows for typhoons, atmospheric rivers (AR), and other extreme atmospheric phenomena. It explores the application of physics-based ML models leveraging OGC standards to enhance cloud-based processing capabilities for tracking, forecasting, and impact-based modelling of Tropical Cyclones (TCs). This aligns with the objectives of D121 - Weather Event Workflows, D131 - Landslide Demonstrators, and D132 - Early Warning Flood Demonstrators. Our approach aims for a comprehensive implementation, encompassing:

- analysis-ready data (compliant with OGC standards)
- workflow models (based on different TC trackers)
- key components identification (data aggregation, normalization, accuracy)
- stakeholder collaboration (understanding, applicability, robustness).

The analysis-ready data part reports various key information sources and contributing datasets, facilitating potential comparisons with ease. This process involved a thorough examination of essential data elements critical for modelling extreme atmospheric conditions, including atmospheric pressure, wind speed, and sea surface temperature levels. The report encompasses multiple steps, starting with data collection which involves aggregating information from diverse sources, including climate and reanalysis data, satellites, weather stations, and ocean buoys. During the analysis phase, various meteorological models were employed to interpret data and identify patterns indicative of extreme weather events, such as atmospheric pressure anomalies, wind speed variations, and sea surface temperature changes. Additionally, workflow models for TC tracking, forecasting, and impact-based modelling were examined, along with the identification of necessary statistical processing steps. Finally, the discussion emphasizes the technical expertise required to manage, integrate, and analyze large datasets and processing workflows, underlining the essential collaborative efforts needed to develop effective and accurate cloud-based predictive Web APIs.

2. Analysis-Ready Data to Decision-Ready Indicators

Examining Tropical Cyclones (TCs) in extensive global simulations covering multiple decades necessitates the impartial and automated identification and monitoring of these storms, a task achieved through specialized TC trackers. These trackers are algorithms designed to recognize cyclonic formations characterized by warm cores within gridded datasets and connect them into coherent trajectories ([Bourding et al. 2022](#)). Key indicators and processes that Machine Learning (ML) approaches are applicable can be identified (see Figure 1) as different forecasting schemes:

- 1. Typhoon Track Forecasts:** Large-scale weather patterns, the sea surface and atmosphere temperatures, features of land topography, structure, and intensity.
- 2. Typhoon Intensity Forecasts:** Maximum wind speed near typhoon center at standard 10-m height and minimum sea level pressure (MSLP) at typhoon center. Wind and gust forecasting and early warning information are very important.
- 3. Typhoon-Induced Rainfall:** Quantitative Precipitation Estimation (QPE) and Quantitative Precipitation Forecasts (QPF) aiming at hydrological forecasting modelling are expected earnestly: quantity, location, and time and duration.

Current challenges for physics-based ML modelling, TC tracking and impact-based methodological approaches incorporate (Zarzycki et al. 2021; Chen et al. 2020; Bourdin et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2023; Bourdin et al. 2024):

- Higher-resolution global reanalyses such as ERA5 produce better global TC climatologies. In terms of the TCs dynamical forecast models, they still have a relatively low accuracy, which is mainly due to the inaccurate vortex initialization of TCs.
- Insufficient representations of the air-sea energy exchange under very high wind speed conditions would hinder simulating the intensity of TCs more effectively. Upper ocean feedback has important effects on TCs, but few operational NWP models take it into consideration via satellite-based data.
- Statistical models, also are unable to deal with the complex and non-linear relationship between TC-related predictors. For the TC size, NWP reasonably represents TC outer size albeit with a small bias and reduced variability compared to scatterometer data.
- In terms of the TC genesis (vortex initiation) and path tracking, if there is no available observed wind speed imagery or in-situ observations, NWP guidance blended with surface observations and partial wind speed images could be used

Figure 1: Cases involving physics-based ML in typhoon forecasting, impact-based modelling and improving Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) methods (Chen et al. 2020)

3. TC Tracking and Forecasting Models

Different TC trackers and databases have been also analyzed for their performance, including those detailed in studies by Arthur et al. (2021), Bourdin et al. (2022), Kitamoto et al. (2023), and Pérez-Alarcón et al. (2024). These approaches are widely varying in their methodologies and application domain, ranging from digital datasets and Python toolboxes to advanced statistical and physics-based ML models. Each tracker/dataset offers unique capabilities, such as the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) and the Digital Typhoon dataset's long-term spatiotemporal data, CyTrack's cyclone detection based on ERA-5 reanalysis data, and TempestExtremes' support for multiple climatic phenomena and weather events. In detail:

Digital Typhoon (Japan & Philippines)

Digital Typhoon Dataset [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git1\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#), the longest typhoon satellite image dataset for 40+ years, aimed at benchmarking ML models for long-term spatiotemporal data. To build the dataset, a workflow was developed to create a typhoon-centered image by cropping the original satellite image using Lambert azimuthal equal-area projection centered at the location of the best track data.

CyTrack (North and South Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean)

CyTrack (GPL-3.0 License) [\[Git\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) is a Python toolbox for detecting and tracking cyclones based on the ERA-5 reanalysis data. performance is cross-validated with data from TC databases (HURDAT2 dataset) and other trackers' outputs (OWZ, CNRM and TRACK). The kernel of CyTRACK is based on detecting critical cyclone centers in the mean sea level pressure field at a single time slice, which are then filtered following several threshold parameters.

TempestExtremes - TE (Regional or Global Earth System Datasets)

TempestExtremes (TE) (BSD-2-Clause License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git1\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) framework provides extensive support for examining both nodal (i.e., pointwise) and areal features, including tropical and extratropical cyclones, monsoonal lows and depressions, atmospheric rivers, atmospheric blocking, and precipitation clusters. TSTORMS algorithmic kernel/algorithm is used based on the TC tracking performance in ERA5, fractional contribution of precipitation from TCs in ERA5 and Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM), atmospheric river tracking in ERA5, extratropical cyclone tracking in CMIP6 data, and finally generation of an atmospheric blocking climatology using MERRA2 data.

TRACK (Global coverage)

TRACK algorithm (MIT License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git\]](#) derives from an extra-tropical cyclone tracking algorithm and it is a Python wrapper package for using TRACK algorithm on CMIP6 data. The rationale behind TRACK is its simplicity as it aims at tracking all vorticity perturbations and it does not embed any warm-core criterion in its initial fundamental detection.

Tropical Cyclone Risk Model - TCRM (Global coverage)

Tropical Cyclone Risk Model (TCRM) (GNU General Public License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git\]](#) is a statistical-parametric model of TC behavior to generate synthetic-event sets that represent

many thousands of years of TC activity. For the Australian region, the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) of historical TCs is used. TCRM uses an autoregressive model to generate thousands of years of events that are statistically similar to the historical record. Finally, an extreme value distribution is fitted to the aggregated wind fields at each grid point in the model domain to provide average recurrence interval wind speed estimates.

TSTORMS – Tcycl (Global coverage)

TSTORMS – Tcycl (GPL-2.0 License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) detect and track TCs in global climate models (GCMs) using data that is typically archived by GCMs. This software uses known physical features such as vorticity, vertical temperature, and moisture structure, to detect storms and categorize them by strength. The advanced version of TSTORMS uses an ML algorithm known as TCycl, and it can be used to detect the presence and location of TCs from certain meteorological fields.

Stormtracks (Global coverage)

Stormtracks (MIT License) [\[Git\]](#) [\[API\]](#) detect and track TCs in the C20 Reanalysis Project (20CR). The procedure (see Fig. 1) uses vorticity maxima to locate potential candidates for cyclones. These cyclone candidates are matched to the best tracks from the IBTrACS catalogue.

CLIMADA (Global coverage)

CLIMADA (GPL-3.0 License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git\]](#) [\[API\]](#) reads and handles historical tropical cyclone tracks of the IBTrACS repository or synthetic tropical cyclone tracks simulated using fully statistical or coupled statistical-dynamical modelling approaches. It also generates synthetic tracks from the historical ones using Wiener processes and it also incorporates methods to download operational ECMWF ensemble tropical storm track forecasts (in BUFR files) and produce TC tracks objects that can be used to generate hazard footprints.

RAFT (US East and Gulf coasts, Atlantic Ocean)

RAFT (GNU General Public License) [\[Web\]](#) [\[Git\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) models the physical behavior of TCs and their impacts on critical infrastructure. A physics-based rainfall model combines TC tracks to produce precipitation at various TC locations. Further, the TC tracks are combined with storm surge, population, electric power, and infrastructure assessment models.

MIT – TCR (Global coverage)

MIT – TCR (MIT License) [\[Git\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) is a TC downscaling model and uses the FAST model to simulate TC intensity. The model is evaluated in the historical period by downscaling ERA5.

CHAZ (Global coverage)

CHAZ (MIT License) [\[Git1\]](#) [\[Git2\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) is a new statistical-dynamical model developed for estimating the long-term hazard of rare, high-impact TC events globally. There are three components representing the complete storm lifetime: an environmental index-based genesis model, a beta-advection track model, and an autoregressive intensity model.

STORM (Global coverage)

STORM (GPL-3.0 License) [\[Git\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) is a novel database on TC characteristics on a global scale using a newly developed synthetic resampling algorithm. STORM can be applied to any meteorological dataset to statistically resample and model TC tracks and intensities.

IBF - Typhoon Impact forecasting model (Global coverage)

The model (GPL-3.0 License) [\[Git1\]](#) [\[Git2\]](#) [\[Pub\]](#) will predict the potential damage of a typhoon before landfall, the prediction will be a percentage of completely damaged houses per municipality. It is based on the 510 model to train a typhoon-impact-based forecasting ML model and it also includes data from 39 typhoons that impacted the Philippines between 2006 and 2020 collected from various organizations and resources and at different spatial resolutions. The typhoon track data are collected from IBTrACS and the maximum wind speed (at a municipality level) is estimated by generating wind fields using CLIMADA.

Model	License Type	GitHub	DOI
Digital Typhoon	-	✓	-
CyTrack	GPL-3.0 License	✓	✓
TempestExtremes (TE)	BSD-2-Clause License	✓	✓
TRACK	MIT License	✓	-
Tropical Cyclone Risk Model	GNU General Public License	✓	-
TSTORMS – Tcycl	GPL-2.0 License	✓	✓
Stormtracks	MIT License	✓	-
CLIMADA	GPL-3.0 License	✓	-
RAFT	GNU General Public License	✓	✓
MIT – TCR	MIT License	✓	✓
CHAZ	MIT License	✓	✓
STORM	GPL-3.0 License	✓	✓
IBF Typhoon Model	GPL-3.0 License	✓	✓

Table 1. Summary of TC Tracking and Impact-based Forecasting Models

Table 1 summarizes the various models analyzed in this study for tracking and forecasting TCs. Each model's license type, availability of a Git repository, and whether a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is provided are listed. These details are essential for understanding the accessibility, usage permissions, and academic references of each model, contributing to the transparency and reproducibility of the study's findings. In addition, the description of features employed by the different models (e.g. data input, parametrization and processes) is presented in detail in the Appendix I (Table A) section.

The integration of early warning flood impact analysis (D-132), which utilizes digital elevation data and river network analysis for flood prediction, with the impact-based forecasting model for TCs offers significant opportunities for synergistic advancements in disaster mitigation and anticipatory action. By combining the precise flood prediction capabilities derived from elevation and river data with the sophisticated TC impact prediction model leveraging eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), we can enhance the accuracy and

effectiveness of early warning systems. TC impact model's ability to predict housing damage can be enriched by including flood impact analysis data (D-132), leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the impacts on communities. This can enhance the decision-making process for humanitarian actors by providing a multi-hazard perspective, improving the allocation of resources, and ensuring timely and targeted anticipatory actions.

4. Critical Factors and Challenges

The most obvious result is that there is a large pool of observed TCs that all trackers detect: there were 3510 tracks in total in IBTrACS catalogue and about 2400 of them are detected by almost all trackers. We end by noting that if one is only interested in the strongest tracks in a simulation, the detection skills of all trackers are identical and nearly perfect. This means that no detected track beyond category 2 (included) is a false alarm, and TC observed with a category 4-5 are found whatever the tracker is. Essentially, because each tracker sets a limit on the spectrum of TCs, and because TC intensity increases with resolution, a more selective tracker (e.g. *TempestExtremes* UZ) is likely to converge for finer resolutions than a less selective one (e.g. *TRACK*) ([Bourdin et al. 2024](#)).

From a modelling perspective, several drawbacks, challenges, and barriers are evident in the development and implementation of cloud-based workflows for TC tracking and impact-based forecasting models. **CyTRACK** demonstrates the ability to detect and track TCs effectively, but its evaluation is limited to specific domains, such as the North Atlantic and Mediterranean regions. **TempestExtremes (TE)**, while evolving to encompass functionalities of other trackers and aiming for robustness across datasets, faces challenges in maintaining accuracy and reliability across different datasets. **TSTORMS-TCyl** (see Figure 2) also highlights challenges in sensitivity and accuracy, as it tends to miss weaker TCs compared to non-ML TC-Trackers. **RAFT** (see Figure 2) encounters challenges related to regional bias and underestimation of extreme weather events. Its intensity model, while trained on global data, performs variably across regions with differing TC frequencies. This regional bias, along with the underestimation of TC-induced rainfall and extreme winds at landfall, necessitates the application of statistical bias-correcting techniques, such as quantile mapping, to enhance the model's accuracy.

Figure 2: (a) Workflows for TC tracking and impact-based simulations based on the STORM (top) and (b) RAFT (bottom) modelling schemes reproduced by Bloemendaal et al. (2020) and Xu et al. (2024)

Similarly, **MIT-TCR** and **CHAZ** models face challenges related to accurately capturing TC characteristics and variability. **MIT-TCR** effectively reproduces observed TC climatology and hazard estimation, but its predictions can diverge significantly in future warming scenarios based on different statistical indices of TC genesis. **CHAZ** captures many aspects of TC behavior but underestimates the frequency of rapid intensification (RI) events due to synthetic storms ending prematurely. Additionally, the model's prediction of landfalls is regionally biased, necessitating further refinement for accurate regional hazard estimation. The **STORM** model's reliance on historical average climate conditions and statistical resampling limits its ability to capture long-term climate variability and assess climate change impacts over extended periods. This limitation underscores the need for incorporating more dynamic and comprehensive climate data to improve the model's predictive capabilities for future climate

scenarios. At last, the **IBF Typhoon Model** uses the forecasts from ECMWF highlighting that they represent the state of the art in TC forecasting and can feed directly into an automated workflow. However, the high horizontal resolution forecasts (i.e. from PAGASA) can be contextualized with their local knowledge, and updates in meteorological variables. It seems that IBF is the more robust and well-tested impact-based modelling scheme and in the future, ML-based dynamic models will be incorporated (e.g. for storm surge) that might improve the secondary hazard features used at local spatial extents (municipality level).

Figure 3: An integrated conceptual workflow presenting the key building blocks based on different TC trackers, input data and ML processing algorithms for TC Impact-based modelling.

To put into perspective the complexity, data needs and processing workflows needed for TC impact-based modelling, Figure 3 illustrates an integrated conceptual workflow presenting the key building blocks based on different TC trackers, input data and ML processing algorithms. The overarching goal is to emphasize the need for robust ML-based algorithms to achieve accurate path prediction, wind and rainfall forecasts, and storm surge forecasts. This requires integrative approaches that simulate the complex relationships between the desired outputs and available inputs, given the existence of sufficient training datasets and TC tracking or impact-based simulation methods.

To succeed in this, Figure 3 integrates various climate model results, statistical processing methods, historical TC databases, in-situ observations, and satellite data sources. Key processing components linked to different TC trackers include atmospheric preprocessing, TC vortex improvement, and data assimilation, for modelling both TC intensity and vortex tracking processes. The workflow also involves probabilistic impact modelling based on TC rainfall patterns and global DEM data, for instance, as illustrated in detail in Figure 3 and Figure 4 of the ER with the Wuhan's Early Warning Flood Detection Model and HARTIS early warning flood detection workflows (D132 of the OGC Engineering Report for the Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot 2024). In conclusion, analyzing Figure 3 prompts us to evaluate the scientific validity of creating cloud-based workflows that integrate various tracking algorithms,

reanalysis datasets, and historical TC catalogues and this will be further explored in the following section.

5. OGC Standards, libraries and APIs

The OGC Standards, libraries or APIs that were reviewed mostly focus on User-Defined Processes for utilizing OGC API Processes to allow users to define and deploy custom processing algorithms in the cloud. This would be particularly useful for researchers and meteorologists to run custom models and simulations based on specific needs or experimental setups. ML-based workflows using different historical TC track data datasets are critical for improving TC tracking and intensity estimation and reproducing TC wind and rainfall patterns, especially for lower TC intensities.

5.1. Data integration

Integrating data for TC tracking and forecasting can be significantly enhanced by evaluating different data sources and APIs. The Python IBTrACS API provides an interface for retrieving TC best-track historical datasets. The Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) API offers access to global and local weather models from different meteorological institutions worldwide, which can be critical for real-time wind, sea level pressure and precipitation data. The ECMWF web API enables data retrieval from ECMWF's meteorological archive (MARS) supporting detailed meteorological analysis (i.e. atmospheric models, ensemble prediction systems, boundary conditions, reanalysis and observation data). Moreover, the Climate Data Store (CDS) API allows access to ECMWF's ERA-5, UERRA, and CMIP5 datasets, which are essential for historical and climate model data. The OData API provides access to satellite data such as Sentinel, Landsat, and COP-DEM, based on RESTful Application Programming Interfaces. Finally, the NOAA – NCEI Web API Services and STAC API facilitate the integration of spatial-temporal asset catalogues for numerous satellite products, making it easier to organize and access diverse satellite datasets. Together, these APIs provide a robust framework for comprehensive data integration in TC modelling and analysis.

- **Python IBTrACS API** [\[Git\]](#) - A Python interface for retrieving tropical cyclone best track datasets (.csv and JSON files)
- **Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) API** [\[Link\]](#) – Retrieve global and local weather models from ECMWF, NOAA-US, JMA-Japan, Météo-France, DWD-Germany, KNMI-Netherlands, DMI-Denmark, MET-Norway, GEM-Canada, CMA-China and BOM-Australia (JSON)
- **ECMWF web API** [\[Link\]](#) - Retrieve data from ECMWF's meteorological archive (MARS) (NetCDF, GRIB or JSON files)
- **Climate Data Store (CDS) API** [\[Link\]](#) - Retrieve data from ECMWF's ERA-5, UERRA, CMIP5 (NetCDF, GRIB)
- **OData** [\[Link\]](#) - Retrieve satellite data (Sentinel, Landsat, COP-DEM) (XML and JSON)
- **STAC API** [\[Link\]](#) - SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog for satellite products
 - On-Demand Production API (production of the Sentinel-1/2/3 products and/or processing Sentinel-1 backscatter and interferometric coherence)

- **NOAA – NCEI Web API Services** [\[Link\]](#) - Access to NCEI satellite, modelled and in-situ data (JSON, NetCDF, CSV and XML) and use custom and standard implementations such as OGC GIS Web Services (WMS, WFS, WCS) and OPeNDAP
 - API v2 Search and access datasets and station and/or location data.
 - NCEI TDS for Satellite/Radar/Model Data
 - Severe Weather Data Inventory - NEXRAD Storm Cell Attributes, Storm Reports

5.2. Data processing

A range of processing APIs offer valuable resources to enhance data integration, analysis, and statistical processing. The openEO API provides a standardized interface for processing large-scale Earth Observation data, enabling the integration of various data sources and analytical methods in TC modelling. The OGC API for Environmental Data Retrieval allows for efficient access and retrieval of diverse environmental datasets, supporting real-time data acquisition and analysis. Through the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) API users can access, process and utilize climate data from the ECMWF's ERA-5 and other datasets. Processing capabilities via the CDS API incorporate statistical processing and bias correction techniques as well as spatial-temporal aggregation and time series analysis. In addition, the GeoWatch API supports advanced geospatial data processing and computer vision techniques to train, predict, and evaluate segmentation models on multi-sensor images that could be potentially used for TC tracking.

In contrast, PyTDML is a pure Python parser and encoder for ML-based tasks including scene classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, change detection, 3D model reconstruction, instance segmentation, etc. It fully supports EO imagery and supervised learning however, it can also support more applications related to TC modelling, like climate prediction, and ground-truth data extraction and handling (e.g. [autoregression models for time series data](#) and [LIDAR, RADAR, Point Clouds data handling](#)). Finally, CliMetLab provides tools for accessing and processing climate data, enabling the seamless integration of various climate datasets transformed into standard Python data structures such as NumPy, Pandas or Xarray, that can then be fed into scientific packages like TensorFlow. Current APIs and Python parsers for cloud-based processing workflows are listed below:

- **OpenEO** [\[Link\]](#) - Geospatial data processing and analysis (arrays, aggregate, reducer, vector, climatology, cubes)
- **OGC API - Environmental Data Retrieval** [\[Git\]](#) – Retrieve climate or reanalysis data, geospatial gridded data, in-situ data, and the ensemble of forecast model data (JSON & GeoJSON)
- **C3S Climate Data Store (CDS, OGC-compliant interface)** [\[Git\]](#) – Toolbox infrastructure/workflows (Applications Use) and potential expansion regarding the processing options. Currently, the toolbox provides:
 - tools that perform basic operations on data, such as computation of statistics, sub-setting, averaging, value at points, etc.
 - workflows that combine the output of tools and feed this as input into other tools to produce derived results

- **GeoWATCH API (OGC-compliant interface)** [\[Git\]](#) – GeoWATCH API enables access to GeoWATCH products through the GeoWATCH web console, Geospatial Information System clients, or through programmatic access.
- **OGC Training Data Markup Language for AI (PyTDML)** [\[Git\]](#) – PyTDML is a pure Python parser and encoder for training datasets based on the OGC Training Data Markup Language for AI standard (JSON data formats). It can be also coupled with STAC API since it converts STAC format to TrainingDML-AI encoding (see Data Integration list above).
- **CliMetLab of ECMWF (ML training and data APIs)** [\[Git\]](#) – Supports ML applications to simplify access to climate and meteorological datasets. CliMetLab includes data import from the ECMWF Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System (MARS) and the Copernicus Climate Change Service Climate Data Store (CDS) into Python environments and allows users to focus on science instead of technical issues such as data access and data formats.

Figure 4: LAAS framework for implementing various operations in ML-based TC modelling, Modified by OGC (2023). Testbed-19: Machine Learning Models Engineering Report

For defining standards to achieve interoperability among/between ML models as highlighted in the OGC Testbed-19: Machine Learning Models Engineering Report and the ECMWF Roadmap for ML, Figure 4 illustrates a conceptual Learning-as-a-service (LAAS) workflow (similar to D131, Figure 7 for the landslides modelling tasks in the of the OGC Engineering Report for the Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot 2024) for implementing various operations in ML-based TC modelling. The key challenges identified for implementing cloud-based ML frameworks underscore the importance of the OGC API for Environmental Data Retrieval in ensuring interoperability with other APIs and data formats, such as GeoZarr¹. In addition, the Climate Data Store (CDS) API and its associated standards should focus on

¹ <https://www.ogc.org/press-release/ogc-forms-new-geozarr-standards-working-group-to-establish-a-zarr-encoding-for-geospatial-data/>

identifying the inherent uncertainties in different reanalysis products across various geographic areas, especially when compared to in-situ data. Thus, there is potential for extending the OData (openEO) Processes to enhance advanced statistical processing capabilities. This extension could include processes for quantile mapping for bias correction on wind and precipitation data from both reanalysis and in-situ ground-truth sources. Also, for wind-related processes, specific methods might be integrated, including moments and L-moments estimation, fitting distributions for extremes in wind and precipitation values, conducting Peak Over Threshold (POT) analysis, and creating Mean Excess Plots.

To discretize the LAAS framework presented in Figure 4, for implementing various operations in ML-based TC modelling, all key components are presented below. The necessary location data for TCs can be extracted from the Sentinel-3A satellite (CDS or OData APIs), the ECMWF Reanalysis ERA5 dataset (ECMWF or JMA APIs), and the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS API) dataset (Tasks 1 - 3). Information related to pre-processing, including data collocation, transformation and integration is provided by the OGC API Processes and pygeoapi for deploying OGC API endpoints for executing data pre-processing as a web-service based on the OGC API — Processes (Tasks 4 - 7).

Data Collection and Integration

- | Task 1: TC Best-Track Datasets (Python IBTrACS API) |
- | Task 2: Global and Local Weather Models (JMA or ECMWF API) |
- | Task 3: Satellite Data (OData API) |

Data Preprocessing and Transformation

- | Task 4: Data Cleaning and Harmonization |
- | Task 5: Data Co-Location |
- | Task 6: Data Transformation |
- | Task 7: Data Integration |

ML Data Preparation and Model Development

- | Task 8: Data Encapsulation (PyTDML) |
- | Task 9: Data Processing (PyTDML) |
- | Task 10: Data Encoding (PyTDML) |
- | Task 11: Data Service (PyTDML) |

Model Deployment and Forecasting

- | Task 12: Deploy ML Models (PyTorch, TensorFlow) |
- | Task 13: TC Track and Intensity Forecasting |
- | Task 14: Precipitation Forecast Generation |
- | Task 15: Impact-based modelling |

Regarding ML data preparation and development, PyTDML data pipes are used, which act as pipelines to handle data flow from raw data sources, converting them into iterable

dataset products (e.g. TDML1, TDML2 and TDML3 in Figure 4). These products are then managed by a dataset encapsulation module (Task 8), which is responsible for extracting and combining training data, ensuring consistency across datasets. Moreover, Data Encoding (Task 9) encodes metadata and data according to different task types, recording formats, provenance, quality, and update information. It encodes transferred data to scene-level annotations, target-level annotations, and pixel-level annotations. At last, the Data Service module (Task 10) offers dataset processing services, including extraction and combination of the trained data using the data loading pipeline. This step plays a crucial role in the workflow, performing all tasks (Tasks 11 - 14) needed for TC tracking, intensity, precipitation and impact-based forecasting (via scene classification, 3D-model reconstruction, object detection, semantic segmentation, and change detection, as described by Chen et al. 2020 in Figure 1). The workflow supports integration with popular ML frameworks such as PyTorch and TensorFlow, ensuring that data is compatible and ready for ML model development and training. This PyTDML implementation is analyzed in detail by Liu et al. (2023) and is graphically illustrated in Appendix II (Figure A).

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

Predicting TCs based on multi-source data, particularly real-time data from in-situ observations and satellites, is essential for improving predictive performance. To this end, detailed historical records of hazard events (e.g., rainstorms, inundations, flash floods, landslides) are essential for training ML algorithms, and it is necessary to ensure that current ML processes and OGC standards enable data interoperability. Thus, current cloud-based processing capabilities must be assessed to determine their potential to support advanced statistical processing techniques. Additionally, there is a need for testing different ML applications to enhance model efficiency, particularly through the use of ML preconditioners for different solvers such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), AdaBoost, Random Forest (RF), and Decision Trees (DT). Feature selection and hyper-parameters tuning might be a complex and challenging task for such ML approaches. Thus, these models need to be further supported by the current Trustworthy Distributed Machine Learning Framework (TDML), as highlighted in the Testbed-19 for ML models (OGC, 2023).

Future steps for cloud-based TC modelling based on OGC open standards should focus on integrating AI-driven ML models with OGC API services to enhance predictive accuracy and efficiency. This integration should leverage real-time multi-source data, including satellite and in-situ observations, to continuously update and refine models. Standardizing data formats and interoperability across cloud platforms will be crucial to facilitate data exchange and processing. For any application platform, system or modelling approach, there is a limit to self-produce everything. However, the results of Feng Chia University's prototype typhoon modelling system and Wuhan's and HARTIS' Early Warning Flood Detection and impact-based models pave the way towards platform interoperability and completion. The integration of HARTIS' Early Warning Flood Detection and impact-based models with advanced TC prediction models leveraging multi-source real-time data and machine learning (ML) offers significant potential for enhancing disaster preparedness and response. HARTIS' flood detection model benefits from precise digital elevation data and river network analysis, which can be significantly enhanced by incorporating real-time data from satellites and in-situ observations used in advanced TC prediction models.

Furthermore, the integration with cloud-based processing capabilities and adherence to OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) standards ensures data interoperability and seamless data exchange across platforms. This is the main reason why standalone APIs are promising (see Figures 2, 7, and 10 of the OGC Engineering Report for the Climate and Disaster Resilience Pilot 2024), and domain-specific datasets can be independently provided by third-party APIs like IBTrACKS, JMA, ECMWF or CDS. The modular nature of APIs for data integration, TC modelling, and impact-based reporting (see Figure 3) signifies a paradigm shift in application development, something that should be further explored in the next OGC pilots.

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Appendix I - Abbreviations/Acronyms

API

Application Programming Interface

AR

Atmospheric Rivers

ARD

Analysis Ready Data

CDS

Copernicus Data Services

DEM

Digital Elevation Model

DT

Decision Trees

ECMWF

European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

EDR

Environmental Data Retrieval

EO

Earth Observation

ER

Engineering Report

JMA

Japan Meteorological Agency

IBTrACKS

International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship

LAAS

Learning-as-a-service

ML

Machine Learning

NWP

Numerical Weather Prediction

OGC

Open Geospatial Consortium

POT

Peak Over Threshold

RAFT

Risk Analysis Framework for Tropical Cyclones

RF

Random Forest

STAC

SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog

SVM

Support Vector Machines

TC

Tropical Cyclone

TCRM

Tropical Cyclone Risk Model

TD

Training Data TDML: TrainingDML-AI

TrainingDML-AI

Training Data Markup Language for Artificial Intelligence

QPE

Quantitative Precipitation Estimation

QPF

Quantitative Precipitation Forecasts

Appendix II – Data and processing steps for different workflows

Table A: Description of the input data and processing steps employed by different models, including IBF Typhoon Model, TempestExtremes, CyTrack, STORM and RAFT.

IBF Typhoon Model: Description of features employed by the different models. Features 1–36 are used as municipality- and grid-level resolution, while features 37–42 are only used as grid-level resolution. For better comprehension, the labels of some features may differ concerning their original labels in the input data. DSWD: Department of Social Welfare and Development.					
No.	Feature label	Description	Local	Global	Global+
1	HAZ_rainfall_Total	Total volume of rain during a typhoon event	✓	x	x
2	HAZ_rainfall_max_6h	Maximum rainfall within a 6 h period (mm)	✓	✓	✓
3	HAZ_rainfall_max_24h	Maximum rainfall within a 24 h period (mm)	✓	✓	✓
4	HAZ_v_max	Max 1 min sustained wind speed, based on wind field (m s ⁻¹)	✓	✓	✓
5	HAZ_v_max_3	Max 1 min sustained wind speed cubed, based on wind field (m s ⁻¹)	✓	x	x
6	HAZ_dis_track_min	Minimum distance between typhoon track and municipality	✓	✓	✓
7	HAZ_SEC_landslide_per	Percentage of houses (OSM footprint) in landslide risk zones (red, yellow, orange)	✓	x	x
8	HAZ_SEC_stormsurge_per	Percentage of houses (OSM footprint) in storm surge risk zones (red, yellow, orange)	✓	x	x
9	HAZ_SEC_Bu_p_inSSA	Fraction of municipality colored blue in storm surge risk map	x	x	x
10	HAZ_SEC_Bu_p_LS	Fraction of municipality colored blue in landslide risk map	x	x	x
11	HAZ_SEC_Red_per_LSbldg	Fraction of municipality colored red in landslide risk map	✓	x	x
12	HAZ_SEC_Or_per_LSbldg	Fraction of municipality colored orange in landslide risk map	✓	x	x
13	HAZ_SEC_Yel_per_LSSAb	Fraction of municipality colored yellow in storm surge risk map	✓	x	x
14	HAZ_SEC_Red_per_SSAbldg	Fraction of municipality colored red in storm surge risk map	x	x	x
15	HAZ_SEC_Or_per_SSAbldg	Fraction of municipality colored orange in storm surge risk map	✓	x	x
16	HAZ_SEC_Yellow_per_LSbl	Fraction of municipality colored yellow in storm surge risk map	✓	x	x
17	TOP_mean_slope	Slope mean	✓	✓	✓
18	TOP_mean_elevation_m	Elevation mean	✓	✓	✓
19	TOP_ruggedness_stdev	Ruggedness standard deviation	✓	✓	✓
20	TOP_mean_ruggedness	Ruggedness mean	x	✓	✓
21	TOP_slope_stdev	Slope standard deviation	x	✓	✓
22	TOP_with_coast	Boolean: coast or no coast	✓	✓	✓
23	TOP_coast_length	Length of coast	✓	✓	✓
24	VUL_poverty_perc	Percentage of people in poverty	✓	x	x
25	VUL_Housing_Units	Total number of housing units	✓	✓	✓
26	VUL_StrongRoof_StrongWall	Number of houses with a strong roof and strong walls	✓	x	x
27	VUL_StrongRoof_LightWall	Number of houses with a strong roof and light walls	✓	x	x
28	VUL_StrongRoof_SalvageWall	Number of houses with a strong roof and salvaged walls	✓	x	x

29	VUL_LightRoof_StrongWall	Number of houses with a light roof and strong walls	✓	x	x
30	VUL_LightRoof_LightWall	Number of houses with a light roof and light walls	✓	x	x
31	VUL_LightRoof_SalvageWall	Number of houses with a light roof and salvaged walls	✓	x	x
32	VUL_SalvagedRoof_StrongWall	Number of houses with a salvaged roof and strong walls	✓	x	x
33	VUL_SalvagedRoof_LightWall	Number of houses with a salvaged roof and light walls	✓	x	x
34	VUL_SalvagedRoof_SalvageWall	Number of houses with a salvaged roof and salvaged walls	✓	x	x
35	VUL_vulnerable_groups	Vulnerable groups from DSWD National Household Targeting Office	✓	x	x
36	VUL_pantawid_pamilya_beneficiary	Number of Pantawid Pamilya beneficiary households	✓	x	x
37	VUL_relative_wealth_index (rwi)	Relative standard of living within countries	x	x	✓
38	total_pop	Total population	x	x	✓
39	urban	Proportion of urban areas	x	x	✓
40	rural	Proportion of rural areas	x	x	✓
41	water	Proportion of areas classified as water	x	x	✓
42	Percent_houses_damaged_5years	Percentage of damaged houses in last 5 years	x	x	✓

TempestExtremes v2.1: Functions implemented for feature detection, tracking, and analysis in large TC datasets based on ERA-5 reanalysis data					
No.	Input parameter	Description - Process	Local	Global	Global+
1	eval_ace	Calculate the instantaneous accumulated cyclone energy	x	✓	✓
2	eval_acepsl	Approximate ACE using sea level pressure (SLP) to predict surface wind speed (ACEPSL)	x	✓	✓
3	eval_ike	Calculate the instantaneous integrated kinetic energy	x	✓	✓
4	eval_pdi	Calculate the power dissipation index , defined as $umax^3$	x	✓	✓
5	radial_profile	Develop a radial profile of the specified variable at each time slice around the nodal feature point by binning by radial distance and averaging grid point values	x	✓	✓
6	radial_wind_profile	This is like radial_profile but for the radial and azimuthal wind speed	x	✓	✓
7	last where	Determining the radius at which azimuthal wind speed is greater than 8 m/s-1	x	✓	✓
8	value	Given an array, extract the value at the specified index using linear interpolation where needed.	x	✓	✓
9	max_closed_contour	Determine the largest value that satisfies the closed contour criteria around each nodal feature	x	✓	✓
10	region_name	Given the names and coordinates of polygons in longitude-latitude space, identify the name of the region for a given pointwise feature	x	✓	✓

CyTrack: Description of specific parameters of CyTRACK for synthetic TCs based on ERA-5 reanalysis data and IBTrACS					
No.	Input parameter	Description - Process	Local	Global	Global+
1	checking_upper_levels_parameters	To evaluate or not the cyclone thermal structure using the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS)	x	✓	✓
2	vtl_vtu_lr	To compute -VTL and -VTU using a linear regression	x	✓	✓

3	max_dist	Radial distance (km) from the cyclone centre to compute the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS) parameters	x	✓	✓
4	dt_h	Temporal resolution of input data	x	✓	✓
5	max_wind_speed_threshold	Maximum wind speed (m/s) within a critical distance from the cyclone centre	x	✓	✓
6	radius_for_msw	Radial distance (km) to compute maximum wind speed around the critical cyclone centre	x	✓	✓
7	outer_wind_speed_threshold	Wind speed (m/s) to compute the cyclone size	x	✓	✓
	filter_center_threshold	Minimum distance (km) between two critical centres	x	✓	✓
8	critical_outer_radius	Minimum radial distance (km) to the outermost closed isobar	x	✓	✓
	rout	External search radius (km) to compute cyclone size	x	✓	✓
9	dr_res	Spatial resolution (km) to compute the first radial derivative of MSLP	x	✓	✓
10	d_ang	Angular resolution (degrees) to construct the polar coordinates centred in the cyclone centre to compute the cyclone size	x	✓	✓
11	terrain_filter	Critical value (m) to discard centres over high terrain	x	✓	✓
12	vorticity_threshold	Surface relative vorticity (1/s) threshold	x	✓	✓
13	min_slp_threshold	Maximum value of MSLP (hPa) to consider a grid point as a critical centre	x	✓	✓
14	dist_threshold	Maximum distance (km) between centres in continuous time steps	x	✓	✓
15	great_circle_distance	Radial distance (degrees) for checking the MSLP increase	x	✓	✓
16	dmslp_great_circle_distance	Minimum increase of MSLP (Pa) from the cyclone centre to the great circle distance	x	✓	✓
17	prev_days	Number of previous days (days) to compute the MSLP anomaly	x	✓	✓
18	mslp_anomaly_threshold	Mean sea level pressure anomaly (hPa) threshold	x	✓	✓
19	intensity_threshold	Maximum intensity (m/s) along the cyclone track	x	✓	✓
20	dt_lifetime	Minimum lifetime (hours) of cyclones tracks	x	✓	✓
21	minimum_distance_travelled	Minimum distance travelled (km) by the cyclone	x	✓	✓
22	VTL_threshold	(-) VTL threshold to classify cyclone according to the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS)	x	✓	✓
23	VTU_threshold	(-) VTU threshold to classify cyclone according to the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS)	x	✓	✓
24	Bhart_threshold	B threshold to classify cyclone according to the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS)	x	✓	✓
25	core_criteria_length	Number of time steps (no necessary consecutive) in which the cyclone satisfies the Cyclone Phase Space (CPS) criteria	x	✓	✓

STORM: Components for the creation of synthetic TCs based on ERA-5 reanalysis data and IBTrACS					
No.	Input parameter	Description - Process	Local	Global	Global+
1	Storms per year	Poisson distribution - Genesis events per year	✓	✓	✓
2	Genesis month	Weighted based on occurrences - Genesis events per year	✓	✓	✓
3	Genesis location	Weighted based on probability - Genesis location - TC track	✓	✓	✓
4	TC track	Movement characteristics - TC track - Distance to coast, landfall	✓	✓	✓

5	Maximum wind speed	Empirical wind-pressure relationship - Wind speed Category	✓	✓	✓
6	Monthly Mean MSLP (ERA-5)	Empirical wind-pressure relationship - Wind speed Category	x	✓	✓
7	Minimum pressure	Empirical wind-pressure relationship and Pressure change characteristics	✓	✓	✓
8	Change in pressure	Pressure change characteristics - Pressure along track	✓	✓	✓
9	Monthly mean SST (ERA-5)	SST/MPI relationship, Maximum Potential Intensity	x	x	✓
10	Radius to maximum winds	Sample from underlying datasets, dependend on pressure - Radius to maximum winds	✓	✓	✓

RAFT: Dataflow for the synthetic TC dataset creation based on ERA5 reanalysis data					
No.	Input parameter	Description - Process	Local	Global	Global+
1	monthly U200	lat, lon, U200, SHRD, Zonal Transpd	x	✓	✓
2	monthly V200	lat, lon, U200, SHRD, Zonal Transpd	x	✓	✓
3	monthly V850	lat, lon, U200, SHRD, Zonal Transpd	x	✓	✓
4	monthly V850	lat, lon, U200, SHRD, Zonal Transpd	x	✓	✓
5	daily T	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
6	daily RH	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
7	daily SST	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
8	VMPI	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
9	1000 hPa	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
10	theta_e	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
11	850 - 700 hPa RH	lat, lon, vmax, rmax, hourly surface wind field (Holland method)	x	✓	✓
12	6-hourly 925-1000 hPa (humidity, shear)	rainfall	x	✓	✓

Figure A: An OGC TrainingDML-AI approach for making EO training datasets ready in deep learning frameworks (Liu et al. 2023)

